

FLOWFI: A HIGH THROUGHPUT FEATURE SELECTION AND ENGINEERING TOOL FOR FLOW CYTOMETRY-BASED SORTING

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ABSTRACT

Fluorescent activated cell sorting (FACS) is a flow cytometry-based multiparameter high-throughput purification strategy for single-cell experiments. Of particular interest is the use of FACS for enrichment of cells that are rare or atypically shaped. Enrichment for such atypically shaped cells can benefit most from new imaging flow cytometry techniques that provide both morphological parameters and imaging capabilities, in addition to the spectral features obtained from standard flow cytometry assays. Flow cytometry Feature Importance (FlowFI) provides a new machine-learning based parameters analysis platform for choosing flow cytometry parameters that are specific to the morphology of the cell in question. Selected parameters can be used to refine the cell purification strategy for downstream analysis, such as single cell transcriptomic or morphogenomic analysis. We benchmark these methods against synthetic data. FlowFI can be used on both imaging and standard flow cytometry datasets with planned extensions to provide tools for novel parameter design from cell images. FlowFI is available for installation and download with a tutorial on how to use the software in combination with real data.

1. CURRENT TOOLS AND DEVELOPMENT

FlowFI tools for .fcs format FC files include (see Fig. 1a)¹:

- Estimation of feature importance using machine learning-based spectral methods.
- Bootstrap estimation to optimise performance on large samples of $> 10^5$ cells (see Fig. 1b).
- Feature clustering and cluster centrality estimation [1].
- Comparison with importance results across cell populations (by saved results comparison).
- Separation of features into types (e.g. imaging or detector type) that can be analysed separately or together.
- Planned feature design tools to include features based on multichannel masks (see Fig. 1c).

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¹<https://github.com/TGAC/FlowFI>

2. RESULTS

FlowFI was tested against synthetic data drawn from a Monte Carlo simulation with $k = 2$ normally distributed and equally weighted cell clusters (totalling $n = 1000$ cells), representing two subpopulations of cells each with $d = 350$ parameters. Performance was measured by the percentage of parameters correctly identified as important (30% cluster informative parameters) versus unimportant (i.e. unrelated to cell cluster). Performance was assessed over b , the bootstrap sample size, which is an adjustable parameter which determines how many samples were used to rank parameters by importance.

FlowFI shows a clear increase in performance (identification of informative parameters) with bootstrap size using a modified spectral method based on [2] (see Figure 1b). This increase saturates around $b = 50$ for this in silico experiment (with $m = 100$ samples). The ideal bootstrap sample size and number is likely to be higher for more complex in vitro datasets, but is still less costly than estimating the parameter importance directly from the full dataset.

3. DISCUSSION

When considering the size of high-throughput flow cytometry datasets, computational cost can limit the scalability of methods designed to identify parameters for analysis or gating. FlowFI provides a computationally scalable approach that has shown promise in synthetic data tests. Further analyses, utilising in vitro data are planned to improve the effectiveness of the method, in addition to new imaging parameter design features for imaging flow cytometry, which should provide greater customisability for analysis of rare cell types.

4. REFERENCES

- [1] Vincent A Traag, Ludo Waltman, and Nees Jan Van Eck, "From Louvain to Leiden: guaranteeing well-connected communities," *Sci. Rep.*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 1–12, 2019.
- [2] Xiaofei He, Deng Cai, and Partha Niyogi, "Laplacian score for feature selection," *NeurIPS*, vol. 18, 2005.

(a) FlowFI User Interface

(b) ROC (AUC)

(c) Cell Masking

Fig. 1. FlowFI (a) user interface, (b) feature selection testing on synthetic data (using bootstrap samples b), and (c) mask-based image features.